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STUDY OF CRACKING AND DEASPHALTING CAPABILITIES OF CATALYSTS BASED ON ALUMINUM-CALCIUM CARRIERS (CEMENTS) CONTAINING NiO AND CuO ACTIVE COMPONENTS

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ANNOTATION

Due to the sharp increase in the demand for transportation fuel, significant changes occurred in the global oil refining industry, which created the need to increase the efficiency of oil use, that is, to increase the depth of its processing with the participation of heavy oil residues in processing. These types of raw materials are characterized by a low C:H ratio and a high content of heavy metals, which cause serious difficulties in further processing with the aim of increasing the C:H ratio by increasing their hydrogen content or reducing the carbon content of raw materials and processed products. ANCs generally make up 25-30% of crude oil, but their share is constantly increasing due to the increase in the production of heavy oil, which is close to fuel oils and semi-tars. Obtaining high-quality motor fuels through the processing of ANQ will allow to use the chemical potential of oil more fully and significantly deepen its processing.

Keywords: heavy oil residual, increase in demand for transport fuel, obtaining high-quality motor fuels

Introduction

Investigation of the thermocatalytic processing of heavy oil residues (HOR), which consists of three stages - HOR cracking, coked catalyst gasification and its reduction - in a flow-type laboratory unit with a fixed catalyst bed with a productivity of 0.068 kg/h, with a productivity of 0.2 kg/h It was carried out in an extended experimental facility with a hot bed catalyst, as well as in a system of reactors with a hot bed catalyst with a productivity of 0.2 kg/h, operating according to a continuous closed circuit scheme[1]. The principle schemes of the devices are presented in Fig.1.

Fuel oil and tar obtained from the oil of the "Oil Stones" field, whose characteristics are presented in table 1, were used as raw materials [2].

An industrial catalyst based on K-22 type iron oxide, as well as re-synthesized catalysts based on aluminocalcium carriers were used as a catalyst. Properties of catalysts are given in table 2.

The scheme of a stationary catalyst bed laboratory unit (Fig.1) includes a reactor, a furnace for preheating and evaporation of raw materials and water, dispensers, containers for raw materials and water, a cooler, a gas meter, a product receiver, and a gasometer[3].

The reactor, which consists of a cylindrical quartz tube with a diameter of 0.04 m and a length of 0.35 m, is filled with catalyst granules and placed in an oven where the appropriate temperature regime of the process is maintained[4].

Table 1

Quality characteristics of fuel oil and tar obtained from the oil of the "Oil Stones" field

Indicators	goudron	Fuel oil
Density, kg/m ³	996.6	921.1
Coking according to Conradson, mass	6.1	3.71
Average molecular mass	500	476
Element composition, % mass.:		
carbon	88.1	87.6
hydrogen	11.1	12.0
sulphur	0.70	0.32
Amount of asphaltenes, mass%	0.90	0.76
Amount of resin, % mass	-	20.01
Freezing temperature, °C	-	5
Ignition temperature, °C	-	168
Melting point, °C	36	-
Amount of metals, mass %. 10 ⁻⁴		
V	-	15
Ni	-	63
Amount of metals, mass %. 10 ⁻⁴		
V	-	15
Ni	-	63

Table 2

Properties of catalysts

Composition, mass %.	K-22	Cement-based
1. Fe ₂ O ₃	85-90	-
K ₂ CO ₃	10-15	-
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.2-0.3	-
NiO	-	15-50
CuO	-	20-35
Thallium	-	20-100
2. Appearance	red-brown	gray-brown
3. Diameter, mm	4-5	5-8
4. Bulk density, kg/dm ³	1.5	1-1.3
5. Abrasion resistance, %	at least 95	at least 95
6. Specific surface area, m ² /gr	10	80-200
7. Service period, years	1.5	1.5

Figure 1. A schematic diagram of a laboratory setup with a stationary bed catalyst

1.9 - capacity for raw materials and water; 2, 10- dispensers for raw materials and water supply; 3- furnace for preliminary heating of raw materials; 4-reactor; 5-refrigerator, 6- product receiver, 7 - gas meter; 8 - gasometer; 11 - evaporator.

I - raw material; II - water; III—reaction products; IV - catalyst; V - gases; VI - nitrogen, VII – air

Methodological part

Temperature fixation along the height of the catalyst layer is carried out with the help of a chrome-aluminum (Xr Al) thermocouple placed in the thermocouple pocket located along the longitudinal axis of the reactor. In heating devices, the temperature is regulated by a type III 4501 potentiometer.

The raw material pre-mixed with water is supplied from the container (I) with a dispenser (2) to the preheating furnace (3), where it partially evaporates, in the form of a vapor-liquid mixture, enters the reactor (4) and $T=500-600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $V=0.5$ As a result of contact with the catalyst layer, its thermocatalytic conversion is carried out at the temperature of -1.5 hours $^{-1}$. The reaction products (III) are removed from the lower part of the reactor, enter the cooler - condenser (5), after that, the liquid products are collected in the product receiver (6), and the gaseous products from the upper part of the product receiver, passing through the gas meter (7), are collected in the gasometer (8).

Then, the coked catalyst in the same reactor is subjected to gasification with steam at $T = 750\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with the help of appropriate transfer of water through the dispenser (10) and evaporator (11). As a result of the contact of water vapor with the catalyst and the carbon of the coke deposits on its surface and the progress of reduction reactions, gas with a high hydrogen content is obtained, which is removed from the bottom of the reactor, passes through the gas meter and is collected in the gasometer.

At the end of the gasification process, which is observed with a decrease in hydrogen yield, the system is blown with nitrogen (VI). Air (VII) is supplied to the reactor preheated to $650\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and thus the oxidative regeneration of the catalyst is carried out, as a result of which the coke residues on the surface are completely burned by air oxygen. The regeneration gas is removed from the lower part of the reactor.

In the "hot" layered catalyst system, the study was carried out in the range of temperature $T=500 - 600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and raw material transfer rate $V=1.0-1.5\text{ h}^{-1}$. The principle-technological scheme of the enlarged experimental unit with "hot" layered catalyst is presented in Fig. 2.

The raw material (I) is fed from the tank (1) through the preheating furnace with the dispenser (2) to the lower part of the reactor (4) and is sprayed into the "hot" bed of the catalyst with water vapor (II) (raw material : water ratio 10:1) from the upper part of the reactor reaction products (III) enter the receiver (6) through the water-cooled cooler - condenser (5), liquid products (V) are collected in the receiver, and gaseous products from the upper part of the receiver pass through the gas meter (7) and are collected in the gasometer.

In the second stage, steam is supplied to the reactor at a temperature of $T = 750^{\circ}\text{C}$ (II) and the gasification process is carried out. The generated hydrogen-containing gas is removed from the upper part of the reactor and passes through the gas meter and is collected in the gasometer.

In the third stage, air is supplied to the reactor and the residual coke is burned at a temperature of $T = 65^{\circ}\text{C}$.

As can be seen from the technological schemes mentioned above, all three stages of the thermooxidation process of ANQ are energy-intensive, therefore, they must be carried out at high temperatures in an alternate periodic mode.

In order to create an optimal technological scheme, each device - reactor, gasifier and regenerator, as well as technological reports of individual stages and heat balances of the process as a whole were made for the purpose of industrial realization of the process. The closed technological scheme of the reactor, gasifier and regenerator, consisting of three reactor apparatuses, was calculated and a laboratory unit for thermocatalytic processing of TKT (thermocatalytic cracking waste) of continuous operation was assembled, the principle scheme of this unit is presented in figure 3.

The raw material mixed with water from the tank (I) is supplied to the primary heating furnace (3) by the dispenser (2), partially vaporized and enters the lower part of the reactor (4) with a "hot" layered catalyst. Gaseous reaction products (III) are removed from the upper part of the reactor and the coked catalyst (IV) enters the gasifier (5). Water (II) is supplied to the steam heater (8) by the dispenser (7) and enters the lower part of the gasifier (5) by turning into highly heated steam. The resulting hydrogen-containing gas (V) is removed from the top of the gasifier, and the catalyst enters the regenerator (9) for complete combustion of the residual coke. The reduced catalyst is transported by air flow (VI) to the hopper (10), and from there it enters the reactor (4) again. Air (VI) passes through the cyclone and is discharged into the atmosphere.

Researches in this system were carried out under the following conditions:

cracking $T = 550^{\circ}\text{C}$; $\vartheta = 1.5 \text{ h}^{-1}$;

gasification $T = 750^{\circ}\text{C}$;

regeneration $T = 650^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure 2. Schematic flow chart of a scaled-up experimental setup with a "hot" bed catalyst

1.9 - capacities for raw materials and water; 2.10 - raw materials and water dispensers; 3 - furnace for preliminary heating of raw materials; 4 - reactor; 5 - refrigerator; 6 - product receiver; 7 - gas meter; 8 - gasometer; 11 - evaporator.

I - raw materials, II - water vapor, III - reaction products, IV - gaseous products, V - liquid products; VI - nitrogen; VII - air; VIII-cooling water.

Figure 3. Schematic technological scheme of a continuously operating unit with a "hot" bed catalyst

1.6 - capacities for raw materials and water; 2.7 - raw materials and water dispensers; 3 - furnace for preliminary heating of raw materials; 4 - reactor; 5 - gasifier; 8 – steam heater; 9 – regenerator; 10-bunker

I - raw materials, II - water vapor, III - cracking products, IV - catalyst, V - HTQ; VI - air; VII – chimney gases;

Results and discussion

The study of the thermocatalytic processing of heavy oil residues (fuel oil, tar, bitumen) was carried out in a flow-type laboratory unit with a stationary catalyst layer with a productivity of 0.068 kg/h. Catalysts based on aluminum-calcium cements with different composition of NiO and CuO (Table 3) active components were used in the research work.

Thermooxidative processing of fuel oil was carried out in the specified catalysts at a temperature of 5000C and a mass rate of raw material supply $\nu = 1$ hour⁻¹. Financial balance and output are presented in table 4. In terms of obtaining engine fuels, light oil products and gas production accounted for 38.8 - 26.4% of the volume, respectively. and 11.1 - 9.8% blunt. 2 and 4 catalyst samples have attracted more interest. From the comparison of the activity of samples I and 2, the Ni active component in the catalyst appears to be more efficient than the active carrier (thallium), the engine fuel yield is 38.8%. 21.3% against The effect of Ni is also manifested in the composition of fuel oil thermocatalytic processing gas (Table 5). Contains 35% crude. High CO² in the cracking process on catalyst containing NiO - 80.15% wt. a gas with a density is formed and a low olefin yield - 3.94% by mass, on the contrary, in thallium - a high yield of olefins - 66.84% by mass. and low CO²

emissions - 9.68% obt. happens. It can be assumed that the formed carbon deposits are partially oxidized to CO² in the NiO-containing catalyst, as a result of which the C:H ratio in the coke content decreases (ie, the coke deposits become richer in hydrogen), which facilitates the disproportionation and saturation reactions of olefin hydrocarbons. In order to obtain reliable and reproducible data, the stability of selected catalysts (samples 2 and 4) was studied at T = 600 °C cracking temperature, T = 750 °C gasification temperature and T = 650 °C regeneration temperature. The dependence of the activity of the catalyst on its working time (number of cracking-gasification-regeneration cycles) is shown in figure 4.

Table 3

NiO(CuO) – composition of cementitious catalysts

Examples	Composition, %mass		
	Thallium (carrier)	NiO	CuO
1	100	-	-
2	65	35	-
3	20	50	30
4	65	-	35
5	65	15	20

Table 4

Material balance of thermocatalytic processing of fuel oil in cement-containing NiO(CuO) catalysts T = 500 °C; $\rho = 1 \text{ h}^{-1}$

Components, %mass	Thallium	NiO-35% thallium-65%	NiO-50% CuO-30% thallium-20%	CuO-35% thallium-65%	NiO-15% CuO-20% thallium-65%
	1	2	3	4	5
Received: fuel oil	100	100	100	100	100
Obtained: cracking gas	5,4	11,1	9,2	9,8	10
N.K.fr.-200	6,6	9,5	7,0	7,5	7,8
fr.200-350 °C	14,5	29,3	15,1	18,9	19,5
fr.350-500 °C	38,8	35,6	40,3	42,5	42,2
residue >500 °C	27,7	7,3	19,5	15,0	12,4
coke	7,0	7,2	8,9	6,3	8,1

Table 5

NiO - content of fuel oil cracking gas in cementitious catalysts. T = 500 °C , $\rho = 1 \text{ [h]}^{-1}$

Components,% mass	Example 1 thallium 100% by mass.	Example 2 NiO-35%, thallium 65% by mass
Gas output	5,36	11,06
Gas composition:		
H ₂	1,81	0,09

CH ₄	11,07	1,74
CO	0,25	5,4
C ₂	33,25	2,17
CO ₂	9,68	80,15
C ₃ H ₈	6,24	1,39
C ₃ H ₆	15,57	0,07
i – C ₄ H ₁₀	0,27	0,28
н - C ₄ H ₁₀	1,52	0,73
(α+ i)-C ₄ H ₈	6,54	0,76
β _{tr} - C ₄ H ₈	1,69	0,68
β _{sk} - C ₄ H ₈	1,72	0,26
i – C ₅ H ₁₂	0,24	1,08
н - C ₅ H ₁₂	1,72	1,12
Superiors	0,34	3,66
C ₄ H ₆	7,8	-
Σ Olefins	66,84	3,94

yield % mass number of cycles

Figure 4. Determination of the stability region of NiO (CuO)-cement-containing catalysts, T=600 °C, 9 = 1h-1

• - sample - 2; ○—example – 4

I – N.K. Fr. – 200 °C, II – fr. – 300 – 350 °C, III – cracking gas.

As can be seen from the drawn curves, the activity of the catalyst increases (the catalyst is processed) and stabilizes (it reaches a plateau) for 5 working cycles (1 cycle - 90 minutes). The yield of gasoline and diesel fractions is 10.5 and 23.6% by weight, respectively. (sample 2) and reaches 9.6 and 15.8 wt.% (sample 4). The fresh catalyst is characterized by strong gas formation. Further

experiments were carried out in the field of stable operation of the catalyst (from the fifth working cycle).

In catalyst samples 2 and 4, the thermooxidative processing of fuel oil was carried out in the temperature range of 480-650 °C at a mass feed rate of 1 hour⁻¹, steam-water gasification process at 750 °C, 1:1 water:raw ratio, and regeneration - at 650 °C for 20 minutes. was conducted. The obtained results are presented in tables 6 and 7.

It was determined that with the increase in temperature (table 6, figure 5,6), the depth of conversion of primary raw materials increases - the yield of gas, gasoline and coke increases, and the yield of diesel fractions decreases simultaneously. 38.8% of the yield of light oil products. The optimal process mode reached is the temperature of 500 °C, at which time the gas output is 11.10% by volume, and the output of fractions is 35.6% by volume at the temperature of 350-500 °C. is. In this case, up to 23% of the potential amount in fuel oil, 350-600 °C fractions and up to 85.0% of the mass > 500 °C temperature fractions react. The quality characteristics of the received catalyst have improved significantly compared to the initial raw material - table 7. Its coking is 75% by volume, the content of resins is 78% by volume. and the amount of metals decreased by 10 times, which indicates fuel oil purification due to the reduction of the amount of asphalt-resin and coking agents, and makes it possible to use the received catalyst as a raw material in the catalytic cracking process.

Table 7

Material balance of the thermocatalytic processing of fuel oil in NiO(CuO)-cement catalysts, $\rho=1 \text{ hour}^{-1}$

Components,% mass	№ 2 NiO-35%, thallium 65%					№ 4 CuO-35%, thallium 65%				
	480 ⁰	500 ⁰	550 ⁰	600 ⁰	650 ⁰	480 ⁰	500 ⁰	550 ⁰	600 ⁰	650 ⁰
gas outlet	6,3	11,1	15,5	18,2	20,5	5,1	9,8	12,5	14,1	15,2
liquid.product.output.p er.hour	87,6	81,7	76,2	72	67,6	89,2	83,9	80,2	77,7	75,5
N.K.fr.-200C ⁰	6.5	9.5	10.2	10.5	11.3	3.8	7.5	8.5	9.6	9.7
fr.-200-350 ⁰ C	28	29.2	27.4	23.6	19.2	19.1	18.9	17.6	15.8	14.2
fr.-200-500 ⁰ C	36.1	35.6	30.1	29.6	27.1	43	42.5	40.8	38.1	35
Fr.>500 ⁰ c	17	7.3	8.1	8.3	10	23.3	15	13.5	14.2	16.6
coke	6.1	7.2	8.3	9.8	11.9	5.7	6.3	7.1	8.2	9.3
engine side exit	34.5	38.8	37.6	34.1	30.5	22.9	26.4	26.1	25.4	23.9
conversion depth	45.8	57.1	61.4	62.1	67.9	33.7	42.5	45.7	47.7	48.4

% mass_t °C

Figure 5. Temperature dependence of the yield of thermal catalytic processing of fuel oil in NiO-cement catalysts

1- gas; 2- fr.q.b.-2000C; 3- fr.q.b.-200 – 3500C; 4- fr. > 3500C; 5- coke

% mass t °C

Figure 6. Temperature dependence of the yield of thermal catalytic processing of fuel oil in CuO-cement catalysts

1- gas; 2- fr.q.b.-2000C; 3- fr.q.b.-200 – 3500C; 4- fr. > 3500C; 5- coke

Conclusion

1. The possibility of applying NiO (CuO)-cement catalysts in the process of thermocatalytic processing of heavy oil residues to obtain engine fuels and hydrogen-containing gas was determined.
2. NiO(CuO)-cement-containing catalysts have been found to be able to deasphalt and demetallize, which allows reducing the content of resins - 5 times, coking substances - 4 times, and metals - 10 times, compared to the initial raw materials.
3. It was determined that the implementation of two-stage thermocatalytic processing of fuel oil using NiO-cement-containing catalyst in the first stage, and KMTSU-B catalyst in the second stage using zeolite-containing catalyst is 65% dull - up to engine fuel, including 31.8% crude with 80.5 octane number according to the motor method. allows you to get gasoline.

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